

Effect of Cr addition and processing conditions on interface microstructure and thermal conductivity of diamond/Cu composite

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ABSTRACT: Diamond/Cu (Cr) composites for high particle volume fractions with advanced thermal conductivities have been prepared via high-temperature-high-pressure infiltration method. The influence of Cr additions on interface characteristics and composite thermal conductivities are discussed with respect to processing conditions. Improvements of interfacial bonding strength and thermal conductivity of composite have been achieved by adding 0.08 at% Cr to matrix, reaching a maximum value of 831.4W/mK. TEM and EDS line scanning analysis show that diamond skeleton has formed in this case. However, excessive Cr additions with 0.4 and 0.8 at% not only impair interfacial bonding and thermal conductivity but also do not favor diamond skeleton formation. Furthermore, the chromium contents favor to the thermal properties of diamond/Cu (Cr) composites are strongly related to the sintering process.

Keywords: *diamond/Cu composites, Cr additions, interfacial bonding, thermal conductivity*

1 Introduction

In the semiconductor industry today, due to the rapidly increasing extent of power density and the miniaturization and integration of electronic chips, the ability of heat sink materials to dissipate heat becomes a very important factor.[1-3]. Comprehensive reviews of thermal management materials are given by Zweben [4,5]. Among them, diamond/Cu composites have received the most attention and have been considered to be next generation of thermal management materials [6-9].

When diamond particles are embedded in copper matrix, interface plays a crucial role in determining the TC of composites, because copper is known to be naturally non-wetting with diamond [10]. It is well known that alloying of copper with strong carbide forming elements such as B, Si, Cr, Ti has been used to establish chemical interaction and promote wetting and bonding with diamond [11-13]. It has thus been shown that the influence of Cr addition on the TC of Cu/diamond composites has been researched by Th. Schubert [11,12] and Weber [13] via powder metallurgy and gas pressure assisted

infiltration method, respectively. However, few researches have investigated those influences under high temperature and high pressure (HPHT) conditions.

In this work, highly conductive diamond/CuCr composites with various amount of Cr addition were fabricated via a new technology, named high pressure and high temperature infiltration method (HPHT-IM). And the present study aims at contributing to the understanding of the effect of Cr addition and processing conditions on interface microstructure, interfacial bonding strength and TC in Cu/diamond composite. A composite of pure copper with diamond reinforcement was produced as reference material.

2 Experimental

Cu-Cr alloys with minute Cr content of 0.08, 0.4, 0.8at% have been vacuum melted in a silica crucible and cast into ingots of 250g, respectively. The used particle reinforcements are MBD-4 synthetic diamonds with a designated particle diameter of 500-600 μ m (mesh28/23).

One zirconium cup filled with diamond powders with Cu or CuCr alloy slice above it was reversed put into another zirconium cup, then subjected to vacuum heat treatment at 823K about 2 hours. The key role of Zr is to eliminate deleterious gas and impurity during sintering process. Subsequently, this system was assembled in a cubic pyrophyllite mold and infiltration was then performed in the cubic-pressing machine at 5.3Gpa and 1373K for 10min. Pure copper was infiltrated for sample A and CuCr alloys with the Cr contents of 0.08, 0.4 and 0.8 at% were infiltrated for samples B, C and D, respectively.

The fractography of the composites was examined on a LEO1450 scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The energy dispersive X-rays spectrometry (EDS) attached to the SEM was used to characterize the distribution of atomic compositions at matrix-diamond interface and on diamond-diamond grain boundary, respectively. In addition, field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were used together to investigate the interface microstructure and production. Thermal conductivities of the composites were evaluated using the laser flash technique on LFA 447 Nanoflash equipment from Netzsch.Lab.

3 Results

Fig.1 displays the fracture surfaces of diamond/CuCr composites with various Cr additions. In Fig.1c and d for samples C and D, fracture proceeds by interfacial debonding between diamond and CuCr matrix, baring the original diamond particles with large Cu pits remaining. The fracture surface of sample B(Fig.1b), in contrast, is quite different. Most diamonds are tightly embedded into matrix and diamonds are even ruptured, indicating that the interfacial bonding is even stronger than the fracture strength of diamond. A relative weaker interfacial adhesion of sample A can be observed in pure copper infiltrated composite (Fig.1a), in which two kinds of fracture modes both exist. Interfacial debonding is observed in this case as well, however, this is not the dominant fracture mode anymore in sample A.

Fig.2 shows the EDS line scanning results for four samples. It can be seen that all the samples feature atomic diffusion from each other, indicating that diffusion bonding between diamond and matrix plays a leading role even though without any Cr

addition. Following the scan path of Fig.2b for example, the intensity of C signal decreases slightly from diamond to CuCr matrix as well as the intensities of Cu and Cr signal increase slowly. Such a diffusion layer was always found between the diamond and Cu(Cr)-matrix for all the samples.

EDS line scanning in Fig.2e was performed on the diamond grain boundary of sample B. The C signal is continuous across the grain boundary; however, Cu and Cr signal is slight. Actually, such a continuous carbon layer was easily detected in sample B, however, hard to find in samples C and D.

FESEM and TEM were used together to study microstructure of the CuCr_{0.08} composite. It can be seen from Fig.3a that the reinforcement particles are linked together, forming short narrow necks on diamond grain boundaries for heat transfer. High resolution SEM (HR-SEM) image of Fig.3b reveals a well-defined, sharp and straight interface between diamond and matrix, which features pretty good interfacial bonding and no obvious interface production layer.

As illustrated in Fig.4a, a sharp line interface can be observed between diamond and matrix, however, no interface production was found in the present analysis. It is worth noting that the diamond skeleton has been identified in sample B by TEM in Fig. 4b, which, in turn, has also obviously been detected by EDX analysis (Fig. 2e), thus indicating a strong diamond-diamond bonding contact in HPHT-IM composites.

TC values for samples A-D are summarized in Fig.5. Obviously, all the HPHT-IM samples were found to have TCs significantly higher than that of pure copper, which is signed by a dash line. The experimental results from Fig.5 show that only 0.08 at% Cr addition has a positive effect on the TC of diamond/Cu composite. Composites at higher Cr contents feature lower TC than that of sample A. Moreover, composite thermal conductivity tends to decrease obviously with the Cr addition increasing slightly.

4 Discussions

4.1 Interface production—influence of sintering process

Chromium carbide is expected to form in diamond/Cu composite interface according to the thermodynamics condition and Cr₃C₂ is the thermodynamically stable production between Cr and C [12,13]. However, our investigation did not

reveal noticeable evidence of continuous Cr_3C_2 layer at interface in all samples. Even so, the formation of Cr_3C_2 , at least locally, cannot be ultimately excluded due to the inherent limits of TEM with respect to the extent of the investigation area covered.

Comparing our findings to those of other researchers [12,13], it is noted that the preparation technology and process parameters are different significantly. In our case, composites were fabricated under an extremely high pressure and diamond particles were tap-packed together before infiltration. When pressure applied, diamond particles with sharp corners push each other and the large pressure stress distributes only on the contact points of diamond particles, resulting in the damage and rupture of diamonds. Hence the diamond surfaces have been degraded with the appearance of numerous micro-cracks shown in Fig.6a. It can also be noted from Fig.6b that, some diamond fragments were distributed within the melted matrix. So carbon sources both from the diamond fragments and diamond particle surfaces are possible to react with Cr. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that Cr_3C_2 was not formed continuously on the diamond particle surfaces but locally exists in all composite and, thus supporting the present findings.

On the other hand, it is also worth noting that the zirconium cup filled with diamonds, however, is selected specially compared to other fabrication method since Zr could aid to eliminate deleterious gas and impurity during HPHT sintering process, which is conducted in a concealed system. However, not expected, Zr can react with carbon to form ZrC easily. Actually, the $\Delta G^0_{\text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2}$ formula differs a little within different temperature region and various researchers have given different formulas, as reviewed by Teng in [15]. The Gibbs' free energies of the two carbides versus temperature have been illustrated in Fig.7. It can be seen that the $\Delta G^0_{\text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2}$ value is always higher than that of ZrC and the thermodynamics condition clearly appears favorable to ZrC. It is suitable to assume that, the presence of Zr may suppress the Cr_3C_2 formation to some extent. From the above points, it can be stated that the processing conditions applied in the present study do not completely favour Cr_3C_2 formation, indeed.

4.2 Composite thermal conductivity-- influence of Cr addition

To our knowledge, interfaces in composites are crucial to TC, as they determine to which extent the properties of a highly conductive reinforcement phase such as diamond can be exploited. Noting that, the composite with 0.08at% Cr addition features a distinctive interfacial bonding and highest TC of 831.4W/mK. One key reason is the formation of diamond skeleton, which provides phonons with a continuous heat conductive passage, clearly illustrated in Fig.3a and Fig.4b. The same result was first reported by Yoshida in [16] using HPHT powder metallurgy method. Additionally, Ekimov [17] assumed that diamond skeleton formation is respected to secondary crystallization, recrystallization and plastic deformation of diamond above 5-6Gpa and 1600K. In our case, diamond skeleton has formed at 5.3Gpa and 1373K with assistance of 0.08at% Cr addition. It can be seen that minute Cr addition may aid diamond skeleton formation due to establishment of excellent interfaces and then improve composite TC significantly. Moreover, the high percentage of diamond (> 90%) is another factor to prompt skeleton formation.

On the other hand, TC decreases obviously with Cr addition increasing slightly respect to interfacial bonding. As seen in Fig.1, the fracture mode has transferred from cleavage fraction of diamond particles to interface separation when adding excessive Cr. Excessive chromium additions can deduce both mechanical and thermal properties of composite due to matrix TC reduction. Similarly, adding excessive Cr do not favor diamond skeleton formation.

It is noted that the result of Cr content favorable for TC dose not agree with the conclusion reported by Weber [13], since the desired add region of Cr content for TC improvement was changed or narrowed due to the Zr cup used in this work. When adding equal Cr content to Webber's work, in our case, Cr_3C_2 production maybe exist locally in composite due to the effect of processing conditions, resulting in excessive Cr remaining in matrix.

5. Conclusions

In the present study, diamond/Cu(Cr) composites have been prepared via HPHT infiltration method and the influence of processing condition and added Cr content on interface production formation and composite TC have been

investigated. All the composites in our case feature higher TCs than that of pure copper, reaching maximum value of 831.4W/mK (CuCr_{0.08} composite). Excessive Cr additions can not only impair interfacial bonding and TC but also do not favour diamond skeleton formation. The desired add region of Cr content for TC improvement has been changed or narrowed under HPHT conditions used in this work compared to gas pressure infiltration technique. Carbide production Cr₃C₂ is likely to exist locally in composite but not along the interface under the processing conditions employed.

Here the obtained thermal conductivities are desirable for heat management materials. To exploring comprehensive performances of diamond/Cu composite an optimization of the matrix and/or the processing conditions is still necessary.

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Fig.1 Fracture surface micrographs of diamond/CuCr composites in various matrices. (a) Pure Cu; (b) CuCr_{0.08}; (c) CuCr_{0.4}; (d) CuCr_{0.8}

Fig.2 EDS line scanning images at interfaces in various matrices (a) Pure Cu; (b) CuCr_{0.08}; (c) CuCr_{0.4}; (d) CuCr_{0.8} and (e) two diamonds grain boundary of diamond/CuCr_{0.08} sample

Fig.3 Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images of diamond/CuCr_{0.08} composite in (a) low magnification (b) high magnification

Fig.4 TEM micrographs of diamond/CuCr_{0.08} composite at one diamond grain boundary

Fig. 5 Measured thermal conductivities of diamond/CuCr composites

Fig.6 SEM images of diamond/CuCr composite with (a) micro-crack on diamond particles and (b) some diamond fragments in matrix

Fig.7 Gibbs' free energies of Cr₃C₂ and ZrC as a function of temperature according to literatures